

absorbance at 400 nm to the correction graph produces Cr contribution at 440 nm which should be subtracted.

Fig. 1. Chromium correction graph.

Determination in steel samples: The sample (~0.25 g) was opened by treating with the acid mixture (15 ml) and analysed as in the preparation of calibration graph. Experiments were repeated with different samples of British Chemical Standard steels.

The waste solutions containing *o*-dianisidine reagent should be carefully disposed or the reagent destroyed either by alkaline permanganate oxidation or by evaporation and incineration.

Results and Discussion

A replicate of six analyses on different amount of samples produced the amount of vanadium that agreed well with the claimed level in the British Chemical Standard steels (Table 1). The interference of Cr, Ni, Co, Mo, Mn, Cu, Al, W, Ti, Fe, Nb and Ta were tested, and only Cr^{VI} interfered by forming a similar yellow-orange complex. The composition of the complex was studied at pH 1 by mole-ratio method and found to have a 1 : 4 metal-composition.

TABLE 1—SPECTROPHOTOMETRIC DETERMINATION OF VANADIUM(V) WITH *o*-DIANISIDINE

Sl. no.	Sample	V Certified %	V Found (n=6) %	Standard deviation	Coefficient of variation %
1.	BCS 251/1	0.65	0.654	0.011 8	1.80
2.	BCS 252/1	0.51	0.480	0.100	2.08
3.	BCS 253/1	0.38	0.342	0.014	5.78
4.	BCS 254/1	0.15	0.160	0.011	6.88
5.	BCS 172/2	0.04	0.042	0.002 4	5.71

The method has the advantage that it can be applied to all kinds of alloy steels containing

chromium and vanadium(v) concentration as low as 0.15–0.65%. The recovery was within tolerable limits of accuracy and precision. The proposed method of correcting the Cr interference is simple and rapid.

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A Spectrophotometric Assay Procedure for Estimation of Fructose in Presence of Glucose

MOHAMMAD LATIF MIRZA*, ABDUL WADOOD and

SHAHNAZ BIBI

Chemistry Department, Islamia University, Bahawalpur, Pakistan

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THE estimation of fructose makes use of its reducing characteristics on its dehydration to hydroxy-methyl furfural and then carrying out a reaction with a suitable colouring agent. However, both these characteristics are also shown by glucose. Due to similar reactions of the two sugars, estimation of one in presence of the other has been proved to be a problem. Resorcinol–thiourea–hydrochloric acid¹, anthrone–sulphuric acid², cystein–hydrochloric acid–sulphuric acid³ and phenol–sulphuric acid⁴ reagents have been used to estimate fructose in presence of glucose. In the present study, we have adopted a more sensitive and equally accurate procedure for estimating fructose in presence of glucose. Two complexing agents, namely, 0.5% pyrogallol/0.5% resorcinol were tested in varying concentrations of either hydrochloric acid or phosphoric acid. These reagents made colour complexes with fructose, whereas glucose did not produce colour under similar experimental conditions.

Standard sugar solution (2 ml) was mixed with either of the complexing agents (2 ml) and the mixture heated for 2 min in a boiling water-bath and then cooled under tap-water. The appearance of

NOTES

TABLE 1—FRUCTOSE CONCENTRATION AGAINST ABSORBANCE USING 0.5% PYROGALLOL SOLUTION

[HCl]* [Fructose]	12 M × 10 ⁻⁴ M		9 M × 10 ⁻⁵ M		6 M × 10 ⁻⁵ M		6 M × 10 ⁻⁵ M		3 M × 10 ⁻⁵ M	
	Concn.	Abs.	Concn.	Abs.	Concn.	Abs.	Concn.	Abs.	Concn.	Abs.
1	0.040		1	0.064	1	0.052	1	0.25	1	0.025
2	0.095		2	0.182	2	0.105	2	0.42	2	0.059
3	0.140		3	0.272	3	0.155	3	0.61	3	0.086
4	0.182		4	0.351	4	0.200	4	0.78	4	0.110
5	0.225		5	0.462	5	0.250	5	1.05	5	0.135
6	0.290		6	0.540	6	0.291	6	1.23	6	0.165
7	0.330		7	0.611	7	0.350	7	1.45	7	0.191
8	0.371		8	0.715	8	0.401	8	—	8	0.210
9	0.415		9	0.801	9	0.450	9	—	9	0.241
10	0.470		10	0.891	10	0.500	10	—	10	0.275

*Less than 3 M HCl could not be used since no colour was developed.

TABLE 2—FRUCTOSE CONCENTRATION AGAINST ABSORBANCE USING 0.5% PYROGALLOL SOLUTION

[H ₃ PO ₄]* [Fructose]	14.66 M × 10 ⁻³ M		13.93 M × 10 ⁻³ M		11.67 M × 10 ⁻³ M		10 M × 10 ⁻³ M		8.33 M × 10 ⁻³ M	
	Concn.	Abs.	Concn.	Abs.	Concn.	Abs.	Concn.	Abs.	Concn.	Abs.
1	0.040		1	0.049	1	0.022	1	0.011	1	0.091
2	0.079		2	0.098	2	0.041	2	0.019	2	0.182
3	0.116		3	0.150	3	0.056	3	0.031	3	0.270
4	0.144		4	0.199	4	0.081	4	0.041	4	0.395
5	0.188		5	0.256	5	0.097	5	0.054	5	0.476
6	0.216		6	0.295	6	0.116	6	0.060	6	0.551
7	0.268		7	0.350	7	0.135	7	0.072	7	0.673
8	0.296		8	0.397	8	0.158	8	0.083	8	0.792
9	0.335		9	0.435	9	0.172	9	0.092	9	0.856
10	0.369		10	0.493	10	0.196	10	0.104	10	0.970

*Less than 8.33 M H₃PO₄ could not be used since no colour was developed.

TABLE 3—FRUCTOSE CONCENTRATION AGAINST ABSORBANCE USING 0.5% RESORCINOL SOLUTION

[H ₃ PO ₄]* [Fructose]	14.66 M × 10 ⁻³ M		14.66 M × 10 ⁻³ M		13.93 M × 10 ⁻³ M		11.67 M × 10 ⁻³ M		10 M × 10 ⁻³ M	
	Concn.	Abs.	Concn.	Abs.	Concn.	Abs.	Concn.	Abs.	Concn.	Abs.
1	0.100		1	0.011	1	0.050	1	0.023	1	0.025
2	0.195		2	0.019	2	0.095	2	0.055	2	0.055
3	0.286		3	0.032	3	0.147	3	0.076	3	0.072
4	0.402		4	0.042	4	0.205	4	0.097	4	0.100
5	0.509		5	0.048	5	0.236	5	0.115	5	0.115
6	0.596		6	0.060	6	0.308	6	0.143	6	0.140
7	0.678		7	0.071	7	0.355	7	—	7	0.169
8	0.802		8	0.078	8	0.403	8	0.183	8	0.195
9	0.903		9	0.090	9	0.457	9	0.220	9	0.205
10	1.002		10	0.100	10	0.501	10	0.239	10	0.243

*Less than 8.33 M H₃PO₄ could not be used since no colour was developed.

orange-red coloration was indicative of the presence of fructose, while glucose did not exhibit any colour. Under all conditions, the systems obeyed the Beer-Lambert law. The optical density was measured using a Uvidex-505 UV/VIS spectrophotometer (JASCO) at λ_{max} = 485 nm. The absorbance of various graded solutions is given in Tables 1-3.

The present method is simple, sensitive and gives excellent results as compared to the existing ones¹⁻⁴, which are labourous and prone to errors. A micro amount (30 μg) quantity of fructose can be estimated if 12 M hydrochloric acid is used as dehydrating agent. However, the sensitivity is reduced if concentrated phosphoric acid is used,

where 300 μg fructose can be estimated. Hence a micro quantity of fructose can be estimated in presence of glucose using the following complexing agents. (i) 0.5% pyrogallol in 12 M HCl or 14.66 M H₃PO₄, and (ii) 0.5% resorcinol in 12 M HCl or 14.66 M H₃PO₄.

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